

Security Framework in Digital Twin for O-RAN

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Abstract—With the vision of 6G networks, the Radio Access Networks (RAN) are expected to entail increased programmability, efficiency, and flexibility. The current trends in Open RAN architecture that promote openness, disaggregation, and inherent intelligence are well aligned with these aspects. The Open RAN architecture’s highly dynamic nature and the data-driven approaches necessitate more cognitive and proactive security measures with robust defensive mechanisms. Digital Twin (DT) is proven to be an ideal platform to integrate into such dynamic systems for testing and optimizing configurations and security algorithms. In this paper, we propose a DT-based security framework for Open RAN (O-RAN) with an elaboration of a use case of security service level agreement (SSLA) assurance management. Moreover, we describe how to integrate energy-aware solutions, such as green security policies, within the proposed framework.

Index Terms—Open radio access network, Network digital twin, Security service level agreement, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The sixth generation (6G) wireless networks are foreseen as intelligent and self-managed networks that provide communication and beyond communication services, considering both performance and value indicators [1]. With the introduction of the Open Radio Access Network (RAN) concept, the RAN architecture is gradually evolving from a closed, unified infrastructure in a conventional RAN to an open, disaggregated, software-based one [2]. This separation increases modularity, flexibility, and optimization while eliminating vendor lock-in. However, the openness and disaggregation of the components in Open RAN (O-RAN) have increased the threat surface by enhancing the susceptibility of each element to potential attacks. Specifically, RAN intelligent controllers (RICs) introduce inherent intelligence to O-RAN by enabling the deployment of third-party applications for RAN management and optimization, including machine learning (ML) applications. Despite the benefits brought by ML models deployed in RICs, they also create novel challenges and some associated risks [3]. During model development, there can be issues related to data acquisition and reliability of the data, as well as threats such as data poisoning, backdooring, and model evasion attacks. In the ML model inference stage, there can be problems with performance and exposure to attacks such as model inversion and membership inference. Hence, it would be beneficial to train and test ML models in a controlled and secure environment prior to deploying them in a real O-RAN system.

Considering the aforementioned security considerations and the characteristics of O-RAN architecture, we identify that digital twin (DT) has a greater applicability in guaranteeing

the deployment and functioning of a resilient and intelligent RAN in 6G [4]. In this paper, we present a network digital twin (NDT)-based security framework for O-RAN and its applicability for ML model training. We consider a use case for RAN slice security service level agreement (SSLA) assurance and describe its applicability within the proposed NDT-based security framework. The workflow for the proposed architecture is demonstrated for Reinforcement Learning (RL)-based model updates. We also discuss how to manage energy-aware SSLA assurance in O-RAN, using an example scenario.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the background and related work on O-RAN security and NDT. Section III and IV respectively present the use case and the proposed security framework. Section V describes SSLA management with NDT. Section VI provides the concluding remarks and the future works.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. O-RAN Architecture and Security

As given in the architecture defined by O-RAN Alliance [5], the O-RAN components are disaggregated into the Central Unit (O-CU), Distributed Unit (O-DU), and Radio Unit (O-RU), accompanied by RICs and open interfaces (e.g., O1, O2, A1, E2, Front-haul interfaces). The near-real-time RIC (Near-RT RIC) operates control loops of periodicity between 10 ms and 1 s, and the non-real-time RIC (Non-RT RIC) manages control loops longer than 1 s as part of the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework. The O-RAN architecture is designed with many security measures, including high availability, secure open interfaces supporting disaggregation, and zero-trust model considerations [2]. In [3], the potential vulnerabilities are classified into two primary categories: O-RAN specific vulnerabilities and general vulnerabilities. These vulnerabilities can be exploited by attacks targeting confidentiality, integrity, and availability. Moreover, the threats are categorized into distinct groups, including threats against the O-RAN system, O-Cloud, radio system, ML system, physical threats, SMO threats, protocol stack threats, and threats to open source code. Readers can refer [3], [6] for further details of vulnerability descriptions, affected data assets, and threat definitions related to O-RAN architecture. A summary of security risks and control mechanisms relevant to O-RAN interfaces is presented in Table I.

B. NDT Security

To enhance resilience against a wide range of potential attack types, NDTs can be designed as a platform to validate

TABLE I: Security risks and control mechanisms relevant to O-RAN interfaces

Interface	Security risks	Security control mechanisms
O1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Denial of Service (DoS) attacks to provisioning of radio elements Leakage of sensitive fault and performance data related to RAN elements Degradation of SMO/RIC functions from O1 data manipulation to harm the correct behavior 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transport Layer Security (TLS) or Secure Shell (SSH) for confidentiality, integrity, and authentication Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) Network Configuration Access Control Model (NACM) for Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF) least privilege access control User to group mapping via Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP), OAuth2.0
O2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DoS attacks to infrastructure Degradation of SMO/RIC functions from O2 data manipulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TLS for confidentiality, integrity, authentication, and no replaying Controls inherited from other frameworks such as European Telecommunications Standards Institute Network functions virtualization Security (ETSI NFV SEC)
A1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DoS or service degradation for O-RAN use cases Leakage of sensitive information such as subscriber's location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TLS for confidentiality, integrity and authentication
E2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DoS or service degradation for O-RAN use cases Leakage of sensitive information which are exchanged more frequently than on A1 due to shorter control loops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) for confidentiality, integrity, authentication and no replay
Fronthaul M-Plane	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethernet frames can be corrupted, delayed, dropped or replayed, thereby disrupting the management and configuration of O-RAN component 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layer 2 security mechanisms are recommended for the M-plane to complement the protection implemented with TLS. SFTP based file transfer over SSH and FTPES based file transfer over TLS or both.

different security aspects [7]. Throughout its life cycle, such as creation, storage, usage, sharing, archiving, and destruction, NDT should guarantee the confidentiality, integrity, and reliability of sensitive data. However, to ensure the reliability of operations and prevent security vulnerabilities in the network application layer, it is necessary to maintain the correct access rights to the NDT layer and follow the necessary instructions. In the NDT layer, the unified data models and data repositories should be trusted, and defense mechanisms for different types of attacks should be incorporated. Furthermore, it is required to ensure security for all types of interactive interfaces, processes, and associations in the NDT. The security considerations are applicable to both hardware and software network infrastructures in which NDT collects data.

C. Related Work on NDT for O-RAN

The use of NDT has the potential to facilitate the management of communication resources in wireless networks [7]. Especially, NDTs provide new possibilities for safe integration of AI/ML algorithms into the network management framework as they provide a way to train the utilized models with up-to-date data from the physical networks, as well as to test the consequences of the resulting network management decisions outside the actual production network environment. Given the dynamic nature of RAN, it is important to consider the trade-off between performance and adaptability when developing an NDT for RAN.

A detailed NDT architecture for 5G and beyond RANs is proposed in [8], derived from the reference architecture proposed by IETF [9]. This architecture encompasses a data repository responsible for collecting and storing real RAN environment data. That data is used to feed the RAN NDT, ensuring an accurate representation in the NDT, with the option to use historical data when needed. The basic models, integral to the service mapping models, comprise representations of network elements and entities. The functional models

section outlines the functions required to enable network-level functionalities in NDT. In addition, there is a NDT management module consisting of all the management functionalities, such as lifecycle management and execution control. This NDT architecture is highly customizable according to the application scenario.

The authors in [10] describe a logical NDT architecture in the context of O-RAN and compare its attributes with both simulator and emulator methods. The paper provides a comprehensive discussion on the practical application of NDT in various O-RAN use cases (e.g., traffic steering and energy efficiency), both prior and post-deployment. The paper illustrates how NDT can help vendors and network operators to plan, test, validate, optimize, and monitor their intended services and applications in O-RAN under various “what-if” scenarios in a risk-free environment. Several use cases that can be deployed through a DT-based O-RAN architecture are discussed in [11]. These include channel modeling for RAN optimization, network traffic forecasting and mobility management, security and threat detection, and network fault detection. NDT would provide the possibility to train rApps and xApps using both real-time and historical data from the network level as well as the component level. The authors identify and address some of the important issues, challenges, and new research directions that need to be tackled for the successful implementation of DT on O-RAN (e.g., real-time synchronization, data flow security and privacy, data annotation, and compliance).

III. USE CASE: ENERGY-AWARE RAN SLICE SSLA ASSURANCE

A typical service level agreement (SLA) represents the commitment of a telco service provider (e.g., a mobile network operator (MNO)) to achieve the requirements (e.g., to reach a certain quality of service (QoS) by assigning network resources to assure given latency or bandwidth requirements)

specified by a customer. A SLA can be defined as an agreement between a customer and a service provider (MNO or digital service provider (DSP)) that specifies the security guarantees or the security-related terms to consider while delivering the network services [12]. Customers provide their intents for security requirements via SSLAs, whereas the MNOs have to prevent the possible violations of those SSLAs. The open interfaces in the O-RAN architecture and the ML models deployed in the RICs may act in such a way to realize the objectives/actions specified in the SSLAs.

Figure 1 illustrates an example of a SLA as described in [12]. An SLA may include both service description terms and guarantee terms. The service description terms may include multiple security services offered by the service providers and the respective capabilities and security metrics defined by standard security control framework (e.g., NIST, ISO/IEC 27002). The guaranteed terms are expressed as security service level objectives (SSLOs) that specify the boolean conditions built upon security metrics such as authentication mechanism, frequency of anomaly checkup, etc. After implementing an SLA, it should be continuously monitored to ensure that the conditions defined in SSLOs are met.

Fig. 1: An example for security service level agreement model as described in [12]

As such SSLAs introduce the ability to establish a consensus on the anticipated security level, which is defined by the security mechanisms and controls implemented within a specific domain, service, network, or network slice. This includes security breaches that are identified, avoided, and mitigated. Furthermore, SSLAs can be linked to multiple security Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as False Positives (FP), False Negatives (FN), and Mean Time To Recovery (MTTR), as SSLAs can be gauged by evaluating these KPIs [13]. Alternatively, SSLAs can establish permissible thresholds for these KPIs that must be adhered to by other security functions.

Considering the RAN SLA slice assurance use case presented in [14], a summary of the roles performed by the components and interfaces of the O-RAN architecture is described in Figure 2. The initial configuration of the slice according to the SLA and SLA can be done by SMO through the slow control loop with the O1 interface. Fine-tuning of the slice configuration during run-time can be done by the non-RT RIC and near-RT RIC either through the slow control loop via SMO and the O1 interface or through the fast control loop via near-

RT RIC and the E2 interface. To balance the QoS requirements specified in the SLA and the security requirements outlined in the SLA and to compensate for potential performance loss in the air interface, Near-RT RIC also has the option to increase, for example, the Physical Resource Block (PRB) allocation for a slice when the security level needs to be increased. All slice reconfigurations should be based on the monitoring data collected from the E2 nodes through O1 and E2.

Fig. 2: Role of O-RAN components for slice SLA assurance.

Security plays a key role in 6G, as trustworthiness becomes an integral aspect of the societal sustainability of the 6G networks. More energy-efficient security solutions are recommended for 6G networks to achieve environmental sustainability. It is critical to intelligently monitor and adapt energy-intensive security solutions or configurations based on the risk level or impact of threats across the system's entire life cycle. The majority of current security solutions are designed as static activities. For example, when RAN devices from several vendors connect to O-RAN, they may have pre-configured security settings. However, during device operation, the degree of security required may vary depending on the specific use case and user security requirements specified in the SLA. From an energy-aware perspective, the optimization of security configurations can be integrated with the delivery of recommendations for dynamically adjusting security policies [4]. This adjustment can be based on the availability of energy resources and the network's assessed risk level.

When the particular security requirements are defined, related energy-efficient solutions can be identified based on the green security objectives to achieve these requirements, such as fine-tuning security configurations without compromising security. The existing SLA can be evaluated and adjusted based on these considerations, with the inclusion of new configurations and green metrics such as energy efficiency ratios and carbon footprint measurements. Without violating the modified SSLAs, dynamic resource allocation based on demand and threat level would achieve higher energy efficiency. For example, by utilizing AI/ML workflows in O-RAN, security resources can be automatically scaled up during peak times and scaled down during periods of lower activity to conserve energy.

IV. NDT-BASED SECURITY FRAMEWORK FOR O-RAN

Figure 3 illustrates the NDT-based security framework proposed for O-RAN based on [8]. This includes three main segments: network application layer, physical network, and NDT. The physical network includes all the low-level components of the O-RAN architecture, including Near-RT RICs, CUs, DUs, and RUs. The network application layer includes SMO and Non-RT RIC from the O-RAN architecture, and it configures and optimizes security policies and configurations at the network level according to user requirements, resource availability, or other relevant parameters. The network application layer connects to NDT via northbound interface and triggers NDT instances for needed activities such as model training, security configuration, and policy verification. The NDT interacts with the physical network via southbound interface. Below, we describe the main components of NDT.

Security data collector: It is responsible for collecting data and logs relating to security operations and configurations. Having the data storage capability facilitates the NDT to have an accurate real-time representation of the physical network and also provides the historical data to be used by NDT instances. Apart from the real RAN data, the security data collector is capable of collecting and storing emulated data from basic network models in the NDT. The security data collector is also capable of retrieving enrichment information from external apps via SMO.

Basic network models: This includes all the related network element models and the topology model. The network element models, such as CU and DU, emulate the behavior of the actual elements, including aspects like positioning, configurations, and operation. The topology would be adjusted to either according to the real O-RAN network topology or to the required emulation scenario. Other models, like channels and slices, can also be integrated if needed [8].

Security functional models: This considers the functional models needed for security operations. The Security Analytical Engine analyzes the related data from the security data collector to establish baselines and detect anomalies, among other advanced analytic actions. The Security Threat Intelligence Engine leverages the feeds from the data collector and the security analytical engine to identify potential risks and threat patterns. With the combination of historical and real-time data, this model can predict future security concerns and provide proactive measures. Furthermore, with intelligent explainability, detailed explanations, and context for the identified events and threats are provided to improve trustworthiness. The security orchestrator is responsible for the coordination of security within NDT, including security policy and configuration management. It provides decision-making capabilities based on inputs from security analytical and threat intelligence models, as well as pre-defined policies. The security orchestrator also includes monitoring functionalities, which provide security insights into the current NDT instance. All of these models can be included with single or multiple analytical, simulation, or ML-based models.

NDT security management: This contains the NDT management functions required for security operations. The NDT lifecycle management model performs the entire lifecycle management of the other models, links, and data streams in the NDT. The NDT execution control model maintains connectivity with the network application layer and the physical network and monitors the execution of the NDT system. The NDT emulation control model is used to configure the emulation scenarios on the NDT based on the requests made by the network application layer. The AI/ML workflow management model handles all the tasks of the AI/ML workflow extended from the network application layer, including the initialization, testing, and activation of the ML model instance.

V. SSLA MANAGEMENT WITH NDT

By combining ML with NDT, the SSLA assurance would be more proactive as compared to conventional RAN SSLA assurance methods. In the first phase, the SSLA is retrieved by the Non-RT RIC via SMO. For instance, the Non-RT RIC can act as the training host for the SSLA assurance ML model. An orchestration function named *NDT configuration function* is also implemented in SMO as a supportive function for the AI/ML workflow. *NDT configuration function* would interact with NDT management models to set up the NDT instance for training, model deployment, and triggering the execution. As mentioned in [15], the model can be initialized by the ML designer or retrieved from the ML model catalog. If supervised learning is considered, a labeled training data set can be generated by using real RAN traffic and synthetic data generated from the NDT environment to cover a wider range of scenarios, ensuring the ML model is exposed to many different situations. The ML model can be deployed within the security orchestrator as an appropriate coordination location for decision-making related to SSLA enforcement and response orchestration. The *NDT configuration function* would configure the NDT instance via NDT security management models and initiate the training process. After the supervised ML model is trained and validated, it will be transferred to the ML model catalog in Non-RT RIC or SMO. Hence, the model can be containerized with other functional artifacts and deployed as an xApp or rApp, as described in [15].

As another approach, in Figure 4, we present the message flow for a SSLA assurance model trained by reinforcement learning (RL). It can be considered that the RL agent resides in Non-RT RIC, which is acting as the training host [12]. The RL agent iteratively interacts with the NDT instance, which provides the training environment. Similar to supervised learning, the *NDT configuration function* is responsible for configuring and controlling the NDT instance. By utilizing emulation control in NDT, RL agent can be exposed to a diverse range of environmental behaviors where enrichment information can also be utilized. By interacting with the NDT instance, the RL agent receives states and rewards iteratively while sending actions to the NDT. Hence, the policy is updated according to the states, actions, and rewards. When the training is complete, the RL model testing can also be performed

Fig. 3: Proposed NDT-based security framework for O-RAN.

utilizing the NDT by emulating different network scenarios as required and triggering actions on the NDT based on the trained policies. Next, the ML designer evaluates the suitability of the RL model for deployment. Equivalent to the supervised learning scenario, the RL model is stored in the ML catalog for future deployment as an rApp or xApp [15].

After the SSLA assurance model is deployed, there can be situations where the optimization of the particular SSLA is required with the arrival of a new SSLA or with the need to update an existing SSLA (e.g., due to changes in network topology, performance degradation, or modified security requirements). To identify their effect on the real network operations and configurations, such modifications can also be tested in NDT before being enforced in the real O-RAN. If necessary, the SSLA assurance model can be optimized using a similar approach considered in the initial training phase. This involves deploying the model in an NDT instance for re-training through supervised learning or by using a RL agent.

When it comes to energy awareness, the SSLA assurance use case can be improved with green security policies. For instance, an anomaly detection (AD) SSLA can be considered where it outlines the terms and conditions related to attributes such as detection accuracy or response time. Prior to deployment, it can be modified by optimizing the configurations in an energy-efficient manner, and some metrics like power efficiency ratios can also be added. A green security policy can be incorporated with the AD SSLA to improve energy efficiency during operation. As an example, if we consider that the AD green security policy includes N sub-policies where the performance and power consumption thresholds are predefined. Those N sub-policies do not violate the AD SSLA, and the best sub-policy has to be selected based on the

intrusion detection performance, the power consumption in the system, and the pre-defined thresholds. Single or multiple AD ML models can be utilized, each corresponding to a sub-policy among other configurations. These models, trained in NDT, may have different complexities and can be either included in an xApp named AD-xApp or stored in an ML model catalog, ready to be activated accordingly. An rApp named policy-rApp retrieves and processes the anomaly detection performance and power consumption data, selects the optimal sub-policy, and triggers the enforcement. This would activate the correct AD model in the AD-xApp, which then interacts with E2 nodes to continue the anomaly detection procedure. In addition to training the AD models, NDT can also be utilized to forecast possible anomalous behaviors based on the current system state and historical data.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This paper discusses the incorporation of NDT in O-RAN, which can provide a secure and flexible environment for assessing O-RAN security operations and optimizations. In particular, evaluating ML security workflows is easier with NDT. To illustrate these, a detailed security architecture for O-RAN with NDT is described. In addition, the paper presents a use case for RAN slice SSLA assurance and discusses the utilization of NDT in SSLA management. The paper also considers the scenario of applying green security policies to achieve energy-aware SSLA assurance. In future work, the proposed security framework will be assessed with algorithms for each model in the NDT and potentially implemented as a system in a real-world environment. Furthermore, SSLA assurance using RL will be simulated, incorporating green security policies.

Fig. 4: Flow diagram, creation and deployment of RL slice SSLA assurance model.

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